

OPTIMUM MODELING OF 3-D CIRCULAR BRAIDED COMPOSITES

Kyungho Jung, Sung Jun Kim, Tae Jin Kang, Kwansoo Chung, Jae Ryoung Youn

School of Materials Science and Engineering, College of Engineering, Seoul National University, Seoul 151-744, Korea

ABSTRACT: An effective geometric modeling is developed in order that precise material properties of the 3-D circular braided composite can be estimated. Most researchers of this field used straight lines to describe their yarn paths in the braided composite unit cell. However, in this study yarn paths are described as curved lines using third order spline, which are close to real geometric formation of the 3-D braided composite. Unit cells should be classified into several kinds because of specificity of the 3-D braided composite. Particularly in terms of the 3-D circular braided composite, a couple of unit cells can be taken. One is an inner unit cell, the other is a surface unit cell. RVE(representative volume element) is also developed. This is the smallest volume element representing whole material properties. All of this research was conducted with the CAD systems prepared by this study researcher and the parametric study was also carried out with this CAD systems. The yarn orientation angle, the yarn or fiber volume fraction and the yarn retraction factor are a function of the pitch length and the mandrel diameter. Based on the geometric model constructed in this research, the mechanical analysis was conducted for the 3-D flat board shape braided composite.

KEYWORDS: 3-D circular braiding, yarn orientation angle, CAD system, volume averaging method

INTRODUCTION

The textile composites are widely used in fields of aerospace and automobile as higher specific strength, better thermal resistance and possibility of easier manufacture by established loom machine. The laminated composites that are well-known material as the textile composites have weak points of lower impact or lower bending rigidity resulted from delamination. 3-D textile composites, however, have good mechanical properties through-the-thickness direction because of existence of reinforcements in the direction. There are many methods to fabricate the three-dimensional fabric preforms. Several famous methods are weaving, knitting, stitching and braiding. Especially, when compared with others, the braiding method has the advantage of an easier processing and it can fabricate various formed fabrics like I beam, H beam and tubular shaped fabrics. That is to say, the three-dimensional braided composite has simple processing method and good mechanical properties in any material direction. Generally the material properties of a textile composite are determined by two factors. One is the component material's property itself and the other is the geometry of each component material. If the textile composites are organized with same materials then the geometric structure is key factor to determine the properties of the composite. Especially, yarn-paths are most important. As the reason, to predict the precise material properties, realistic modeling of the geometry is needed. In the early works of geometric study, most researchers studied rectangle braided structure that means the cross-section shape is rectangle and a unit cell of theirs is simple and has 4 yarns described as straight line. Ko et al. [1][9] studied a similar part of the braided geometry. It was revealed by R. Pandey [2] that Ko's unit cell is the same with the Li's one except a position in the braided

preform. R. Pandey modeled the geometry using CAD system. He considered the yarn jamming condition and crimp. Using the condition he varied the yarn cross-section area to vary the yarn volume fraction that is connected with yarn jamming and crimp. But he assumed that the yarn paths are straight. L. Chen et al. [3] and Byun [4][11] divided the unit cell into several groups because of specificity of the braided structure. L. Chen's unit cells are corner unit cell, surface unit cell and interior unit cell. And he assumed the yarn cross-section shape is elliptic. With the unit cells he studied the geometry and defined a useful theoretical maximum yarn volume fraction. Youqi Wang [5] developed dynamic CAD system considering braiding process, yarn's friction, applied force and yarn's contact conditions. With this CAD system virtual braiding process and braided preform was constructed and he studied the geometry using his virtual preform. Brunnschweiler [6] used the Peirce's theory and S.V.Lomov [8] used twill structure. Few researches on the 3-D circular braided preform have been reported for the rectangle-braided structure. In field of the mechanical analysis, Ko demonstrated that tensile strength of the braided composites is greater than that of laminated composites. Masters [10] used the laminate model, diagonal brick model and FEM. He mentioned that first two models were well agreed and the latest model has excellent agreement. But the laminate model and diagonal brick model can't explain an undulation of yarns through-the-thickness direction and FEM requires unique computer code for each structures. Smith [12] used the fiber inclination model as well as the laminated model and he used the maximum fiber strain model for analyzing the fracture. The fiber inclination model was more precise than the laminated model. But like Masters, his model can't consider the undulation of yarns. Byun et al. [11] propose the averaging method to analyze the braided structure. This model has a good point that it considers the undulation of yarns and it is flexible method to the braided structure that is sensitive in geometry. The key issue in the braided structure is to model precise geometry and to analyze the precise properties of the braided structure based on the precise geometry

PROCESS

The machine used in this research is vertical type circular 4-step machine. On the machine bed there are many carriers, which move interlacing yarns. The number of carriers in both of circumferential and radial direction on the machine bed is important processing variable in addition to connected yarn number. The dimension of used yarn is also important processing variable. In this research, yarn cross-section is assumed as an ellipse.

A tubular shaped preform can be made using circular braiding machine. A mandrel is placed in the center of braiding yarns and then yarns are interlaced around the mandrel during the process. Variable shape of mandrel can be used. When a cylindrical mandrel is used, the diameter of mandrel is important processing variable. The braiding process can be divided into two motions. One is a step motion and the other is a beating motion. During the step motion, moving carriers make the yarns interlaced. Fig. 1 shows the 4 steps of 4-step machine.

Fig. 1 Step motions of circular 4-step machine

Because the cycle is repeated, the braided preform has repeated structures. One “Repeat” means the situation that all carriers return to their original position after a certain cycle. The number of cycle for one Repeat is yield by RCN and CCN.

$$C = \frac{RCN}{2(RCN - 1)} \times LCM(CCN, 2(RCN - 1))$$

Where, C = the number of operating cycles to form a Repeat

RCN = the number of carriers in the radial direction

CCN = the number of carriers in the circumferential direction

LCM = the least common multiple of CCN and 2(RCN-1)

Carriers can be classified by its trace on the machine bed. It is refer to as a carrier group. The more carrier groups, the more compact and dense preform can be maid. The number of group (G) can be yield by RCN and CCN.

$$G = \frac{2(RCN - 1)CCN}{LCM(2(RCN - 1), CCN)}$$

The beating motion, which plays a role of compacting and unifying the braided structure, is related with yarn or fiber volume fraction. A shape of 3-D circular braided preform resembles a machine setting mentioned before. If a preform pattern is denoted as M×N then the preform has M layers in preform radial direction and has N sets of yarns in preform circumferential direction.

GEOMETRIC MODELING

The 3-D circular braiding process is composed of two kinds of motions. One is a beating motion and the other is a step motion. The step motion is divided into two types, that is, two steps and four steps that play an important role in determining structure of braided preforms. In the circular 4-step process, one cycle that means the number of steps to get the same arrangement of carriers is composed of four steps, which are clockwise, counterclockwise, ring out and ring in. As this periodic carrier motion determines the geometry of the 3-D circular braided preform, in this research, the geometric modeling was performed on the basis of the carrier movements in one cycle. Any size of broken pieces can be a unit cell, but as a matter of convenience the smallest gets to be a unit cell. Therefore, the smallest quadratic lattice passed by carriers on the machine bed can be considered as an element to make the unit cell. The smallest quadratic lattice used, 12 unit cells can exist in the circumferential direction in the machine bed set by 3x12 which means 3 carriers existing in the radial direction and 12 carriers in the circumferential direction. The inner unit cell located in the inner part of the structure can be

constructed firstly by determining its size and secondly by determining the yarn paths in it. The number of carriers used determines the size of unit cell. Also, the movement of carriers as well as contact conditions determines yarn paths existing in a unit cell. Fig. 2 and 3 show the carrier motion and yarn paths of IUC (Inner Unit Cell) and SUC (Surface Unit Cell), respectively.

Fig. 2 The inner carrier motion and yarn paths of IUC

Fig. 3 The outer carrier motion and yarn paths in SUC

To do this, some assumptions should be adopted that elliptic cross-section of yarns has an unchangeable minor axis and yarns contact each other only at the minor axis direction in XY plane. 6 data points could be obtained from the carrier motion and the assumption. Spline describing a yarn path can be calculated with these data points. In this study the spline having 12 unknowns is composed of 3 individual functions. 12 unknowns could be found from these known 6 points (6 conditions), from the connected end point of the individual functions in which differential values must be the same (4 conditions), and from the normal conditions between boundaries of the unit cell and the spline (2 conditions).

The method forming the surface unit cell is same, except that it is divided into two kinds, namely, the ISUC (interior surface unit cell) and ESUC (exterior surface unit cell). The former is exposed on the surface of preform and the latter comes in contact with mandrel on which yarns are braided. RVE(Representative Volume Element) could be constructed by combining these unit cells. The structures of unit cells and the graphical development of RVE are shown in Fig. 4 and 5, respectively.

Fig. 4 The graphical development of (a) IUC (b) ESUC (c) ISUC

Fig. 1 The graphical development of (a) RVE (b) RVE in X-Y plane

The number of radial direction carriers is also one of the important factors in determining the structure of RVE. If 7 carriers exist in the radial direction on the machine bed, there are 7 individual unit cells including 2 surface unit cells, the exterior and the interior. The preform having this RVE is defined to 6 layers. A wide range of preform was conducted and compared with a real preform manufactured by the researcher of this study so that the validity of this geometric modeling can be proven.

Fig. 2 The graphical development of
 (a) 12 layers preform (b) 1 layer preform (c) orthogonal view

Especially, It was assumed that the maximum yarn or fiber volume fraction is formed by excess beating motion, when the cross-section shape of yarns were achieved into circle by compressing the major axis of yarn cross-section. Fig. 7 shows the IUC in normal condition and in maximum yarn volume fraction (MYVF) condition.

Fig. 3 Graphical development of (a) initial condition (b) MYVF condition by the CAD system

GEOMETRIC STUDY OF THE 3-D CIRCULAR BRAIDED PREFORM

Using the modeling method, the CAD system for the 3-D circular braided preform was developed. Because the modeled yarn paths, UCs, and RVE is coded in vector form using computer C⁺⁺ language in global coordinate system X-Y-Z. So the CAD system can calculate the useful data by numerical method. For example, area of yarn-cross-section, a length of yarn paths and volume, orientation angle of infinitesimal yarn's cross-section and UC's volume and so on. So the geometric study of the 3-D circular braided preform can be done with the CAD system.

YARN RETRACTION FACTOR (YRF)

Yarn retraction factor (hereinafter refer to as YRF) is defined that a ratio of used length of a yarn to a length of fabric. It close to 1 in unidirectional textile composite but it is larger than 1 in three

dimensional textile composite. YRF is useful geometric factor to design the fabric length because the length of used yarns can be calculated to manufacture certain length of fabric. It can be easily defined in individual unit cells as

$$YRF(i) = \frac{L(i)}{PL}$$

Where, i = the unit cell number

$L(i)$ = the length of a yarn that a unit cell contains

PL = the pitch length

Average value can be taken for the whole braided preform YRF so

$$YRF = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{RCN-1} YRF(i)}{RCN}$$

Since this geometric study is carried out with the CAD system, for the general calculation of geometric factors, general mathematical equation of YRF for the whole braided composite is needed. The equation of YRF as a function of processing variables and length of used yarn can be yield based on the modeling as

$$YRF = \frac{L}{PL \times CN}$$

Where L = the used yarn length

CN = total cycle number after the braiding process

YARN ORIENTATION ANGLE (YOA)

Yarn orientation angle (hereinafter refer to as YOA) is important geometric factor as it is directly connected with a directional rigidity of the composite. It is defined as the angle between spatial arranged yarns and fabricating direction. So in individual unit cells

$$YOA(i) = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{PL}{L(i)}\right)$$

Where, i = the unit cell number

$L(i)$ = the length of a yarn that a unit cell contains

PL = the pitch length

Also, the YOA has a relation with YRF. It can be easily found from the both of the definitions.

$$\cos(YOA(i)) \times YRF(i) = 1$$

Average value can be taken for the whole braided preform YOA like the YRF so

$$YOA = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{RCN-1} YOA(i)}{RCN}$$

From the relation, mathematical equation of the YOA can be yield by using the YRF as

$$YOA = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{1}{YRF}\right)$$

YARN VOLUME FRACTION

Yarn volume fraction (hereinafter refer to as YVF) plays a role of a rigidity or stiffness of the composite. From the definition, the numerical expression of the YVF in individual unit cell is yield as

$$YVF(i) = \frac{V(i)_{Yarn,UC}}{V(i)_{UC}}$$

Where, $V(i)_{Yarn,UC}$ = the volume of yarns

$V(i)_{UC}$ = the volume of the unit cell

Average value of YVF can't be taken for the whole braided preform because of existence of void space in RVE. So the YVF in the RVE can be taken for the whole braided preform YVF so

$$YVF = \frac{V_{Yarn,RVE}}{V_{RVE}}$$

Where, $V_{Yarn,RVE}$ = the volume of yarns in the RVE
 V_{RVE} = the volume of the RVE.

General mathematical form of The YVF can be yield as a function of YRF and processing variables.

$$V_{Yarn,RVE} \approx 2\pi ab \times PL \times YRF \times RCN$$

The reason why $V_{Yarn,RVE}$ is approximated is because a clipping volume of yarns that protrudes out of RVE exists. Where a and b are the major, minor radius of yarn cross-section respectively. From the modeling of the RVE, the volume of the RVE can be easily expressed to a numerical formula so

$$V_{RVE} = 8\pi b(R + (RCN + 1)b)(RCN + 1) \frac{PL}{CCN}$$

Where R is the radius of the mandrel. And from the results, YVF can be yield as a following.

$$YVF \approx \frac{a \times YRF \times RCN \times CCN}{4(R + (RCN + 1)b)(RCN + 1)}$$

DISCUSSIONS

The parametric study was performed with the CAD systems prepared by these researchers. We divided the unit cell into three sub unit cells, which are exterior-surface unit cell, interior-surface unit cell and inner unit cell. The yarn paths are determined using third order spline function. RVE(Representative Volume Element) is constructed by combining those unit cells. The yarn orientation angle, the yarn or fiber volume fraction and the yarn retraction factor are a function of the pitch length and the mandrel diameter.

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